

CONTROL PROBLEMS IN POWER SYSTEMS AND EXPERT SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The article offers an overview and analysis of energy system control problems. It considers the current state and prospects for the creation and use of expert systems for power system control and substantiates the necessity of using expert systems for multi-criteria control of power systems' normal daily regimes.

It is shown that the scope of application of expert systems in the energy sector is quite wide: planning of power system modes, control and control of electric power systems, restoration of power supply after an accident, identifying locations of faults in the power grid, analysis of power grid operating modes, control of flows in networks, forecasting, and planning of operating modes of equipment and systems dispatch control, etc.

Keywords: power systems, expert systems, energy system problems, decision making-problems, multicriteria systems.

As you know, a person, an expert plays a central role in the decision-making process. This role becomes even more important when making decisions in multicriteria energy systems. It is well known that the capabilities of a decision-maker in multicriteria systems when making decisions are very limited [1-8]. Many decision-making problems with a certain number of criteria and a certain nature become very complex for the decision-maker. When solving such problems, he makes mistakes and uses heuristics. There are certain limits to the decision-maker's capabilities for any decision-making task. These restrictions depend on the number of criteria, requirements for results, etc. Outside these limits, he no longer uses a significant part of the information, violates the condition of transitivity, the condition of repeatability of assessments in the same situation, etc.

When making decisions in multicriteria systems, the decision-maker performs several operations that can be divided into four groups [1-3] a) Operations on criteria names; b) Operations on individual values of the criteria of one alternative; c) Operations on the set of values of all criteria of one alternative; d) Operations on variables. These operations include elementary suboperations. They are divided into three categories based on complexity: complex, valid, and indeterminate operations. Undefined elementary operations are divided into indefinitely complex and indefinitely valid elementary operations.

The operations of the first group include the following elementary suboperations: a) Assign weights to the criteria. Typically, it is difficult for the decision-maker to assign weights to the criteria. Therefore, this elementary operation belongs to the category of complex operations. b) Ordering the criteria by importance. For the decision maker, performing this operation is not difficult, so this operation can be classified as an acceptable operation in terms of complexity [2-4].

The operations of the second group include the following elementary suboperations:

1. Comparison of two values of one criterion. This operation is quite simple for the decision-maker. Therefore, it belongs to the category of permissible operations;

2. Comparison of the values of two different criteria with fixed values of other criteria. This operation is easily performed by the decision maker, and therefore belongs to the category of permissible operations;

3. Quantitative assessment of changes in the value of one criterion. It is usually difficult for the decision-maker to quantify the change in criterion value. Therefore, it can be described as an indefinitely complex operation;

4. Determination of a satisfactory value based on one criterion. For the decision maker, performing this operation is not difficult. No psychological tests have been conducted in this area, so this operation falls into the category of uncertain permissible operations;

5. Identification of some or all criteria whose values should be improved, may worsen, or should not change. Performing such an operation is not difficult for the decision-maker, so it can be classified as a permissible operation;

6. Selection of criteria whose values are the most unsatisfactory. For the decision-maker, performing such an operation is not difficult. Therefore, this operation may fall into the category of acceptable operations.

The operations of the third group include the following elementary suboperations:

1. Comparing two alternatives and choosing the best. If the number of criteria exceeds three, then this operation is quite complicated for the decision-maker. Therefore, it belongs to the category of complex operations;

2. Selecting the best alternative from several possible options. This operation is quite complex for the decision-maker. Therefore, it belongs to the category of complex operations;

3. Finding an ideal alternative, proximity to which determines the quality of the current solution. This operation is quite complex for the decision-maker. Therefore, it belongs to the category of complex operations.

The operation of the fourth group includes the following elementary suboperation - identification of variables whose values should be increased. This operation is difficult for the decision-maker. There has been no systematic research in this direction, so this operation can be classified as an undetermined complex operation.

When comparing multicriteria alternatives, the decision maker uses compensation and exclusion strategies. The following compensation strategies exist: a) Determining the advantages of each alternative and comparing them; b) Calculation of differences in ratings for each criterion and subsequent summation of these differences. The following exclusion strategies exist: a) Elimination of criteria using their scores; b) Sequential exclusion of criteria.

When evaluating multi-criteria alternatives, the decision maker uses the following heuristic rules: a) counts the number of criteria by which one alternative is better than another, and selects the alternative by which this number is greater; b) Criteria according to which the difference between the assessments of alternatives is small are often not taken into account; c) Eliminates criteria considered sequentially.

The mentioned heuristics are often used by the decision maker, even when there are a small number of criteria and alternatives (up to three criteria or alternatives). The fact is that he cannot simultaneously have in memory two sets of evaluations of two alternatives when comparing them. On the other hand, the use of heuristic rules leads to errors and contradictions. Therefore, it is necessary to develop special methods for obtaining information from the decision maker, taking into account his limited capabilities and not requiring him to use heuristics.

Over the past three decades, expert systems have been increasingly used in multi-criteria decision-making. The classification of decision-making problems from the point of view of expert systems, the structure of the decision-making process, etc. are given in works [1-5]. The main sources of knowledge in such decision-making systems are: specialists in the relevant field, experience gained during the operation of the system, literature, etc. The decision-making structure is presented in the form of "if-then" production rules.

Several works discuss issues of decision-making using expert systems [6]. The proposed approach allows us to formulate the relations of knowledge and preferences of the decision-maker in the form of formal facts and rules. The hierarchical control mechanism based on expert rules and the structure of the decision-making system are described. The decision-making problem is considered a problem in the development of artificial intelligence systems. Requirements for the structure and capabilities of expert systems are formulated. The stages of the decision-making process are discussed from the point of view of their possible formalization. The issues of using expert systems in making complex decisions are discussed.

A relatively small amount of work is devoted to the use of expert systems in multicriteria systems, in particular in energy systems, when making decisions. In [7] the issues of using expert systems when making

decisions in such systems are discussed. When making decisions, knowledge about alternatives, goals, criteria, and their connections is used. Knowledge is accumulated in the form of a semantic tree, aggregation function, or alternatives. The semantic tree reflects the structure of the decision-making problem through the decomposition of criteria; aggregation functions are determined by the rules for summing criteria values; and the alternatives are described by the values of the elementary criteria of the tree. Knowledge is used to evaluate alternatives and order them. The user is advised to select a better alternative.

There are two approaches to the use of expert systems when making decisions in multicriteria systems, in particular in energy systems. The first approach is based on models, and the second is based on heuristics. In the first case, the decision maker makes decisions based on a formal model, and in the second, based on heuristic rules. Expert systems are considered an effective means of making recommendations. It is noted that it is especially effective to combine model decision-making methods with expert systems.

As a rule, expert systems are designed to solve informal or weakly formalized problems when algorithms and methods for solving the problem are unknown. Expert systems, which are specialized computer systems, are capable of collecting and summarizing the empirical experience of highly qualified specialists (power system dispatchers) in a given subject area (for example, managing the daily regimes of power systems) and providing advice to specialists. Expert systems use the structured knowledge and experience of highly skilled power system managers to provide effective solutions.

Experts make decisions and acceptable results based on their empirical knowledge and experience. To ensure the effective functioning of expert systems, they must be able to acquire knowledge and use it effectively. Much attention to the problem of acquiring knowledge is because it is a scarce resource and is expensive. Since knowledge is a basic and expensive resource, it is quite justified to spend large amounts of money on acquiring knowledge and its computerization.

One of the multicriteria systems where these problems are most acute is the energy system. The modern energy system is a very complex and difficult-to-formalize object, the control, modernization, and development of which requires the introduction and use of new control methods. The increasing accuracy of power system models, the increasing complexity of network circuits, tightening requirements for quality and energy savings, etc. have made it necessary to use new control systems based on expert knowledge in the field of energy.

One of the areas of effective control of energy systems is the use of expert systems. The use of artificial intelligence systems, in particular, expert systems, in the energy sector is determined by such specific features of the energy sector as: significant distribution in space, heterogeneity and variety of devices, the use of

automatic and non-automatic control methods, insufficient information in emergency situations and in emergencies and the post-emergency period, etc.

The use of expert systems in the energy sector provides the following advantages: the ability to quickly analyze the situation during emergency processes, use the experience of qualified workers in controlling the restoration of normal conditions after emergency violations, justification and explanation of recommendations issued, which allows low-skilled workers to accumulate knowledge, etc. When developing expert systems for power systems, the following problems usually arise: difficulties in mutual understanding between developers and users, difficulties in considering additional conditions, challenges in developing rules for rare emergency violations, etc.

Currently, expert systems are used in the following areas of energy: control and monitoring of the state of the power system, planning of power system modes, design of power system devices, solving operational problems such as reliability analysis, detection of fault locations, emergency control, disaster recovery, signal generation and processing alarms, control of device states, personnel training and advanced training, regulation of active and reactive power, voltage regulation, analysis of network modes, control of the development of networks and systems, etc.

In the last two decades, expert systems have been used to solve energy problems, such as forecasting electricity consumption, forecasting water resources, planning modes, etc. Expert systems are characterized by the scalability of the problems they solve, high reliability, and focus on long-term operation. Their structure should contain an information base, information sources, and several specialized consumer systems designed to solve various energy problems. Expert systems are usually used to solve energy problems for which no formal algorithmic description exists.

Several works [6-8] were devoted to substantiating the need to use expert systems in the control of energy systems. The main functions that expert systems must perform are defined: as collection and interpretation of data, regulation, determining the adequacy of initial data and the reaction of objects, forecasting events, and planning power system modes based on comparison of old and new data.

Currently, expert systems are a promising and necessary means of solving many complex practical problems in the energy sector. Expert systems make it possible to better take into account the characteristics of energy systems and effectively use the knowledge of specialists. At the same time, many potential problems arise when using expert systems in the energy sector. Therefore, scientific research in this direction should be strengthened.

To effectively control the modes of modern energy systems, a large amount of special knowledge is required [7-8]. This knowledge can be successfully used through expert systems. Expert systems are used to solve problems in which specialists with specialized data, knowledge, and experience play an important role.

Currently, promising areas of application of expert systems in the energy sector are: forecasting and planning of equipment operating modes; Drawing up operational activities and programs for performing operations to manage energy systems; and creation of warning systems and diagnostic systems.

One of the strategic directions for using expert systems in the energy sector is operational dispatch control. A large number of works are devoted to issues related to the use of expert systems in the operational control of energy systems. Also, many works are devoted to the use of expert systems in dispatch control systems. Many works substantiate the need to use expert systems in dispatch control.

Many expert systems are used to dispatch start-ups and shutdowns of power units. In this direction, the use of expert systems with the knowledge and experience of power system operators will provide a service to unqualified operators when making decisions.

Several works [4-8] are devoted to the use of expert systems in controlling flows in energy networks. The main goal of the development, implementation and use of expert systems for controlling flows in networks is to generalize the experience of qualified personnel, and reduce the likelihood of erroneous actions by personnel. The success of implementing expert systems significantly depends on solving the following problems: fast information processing, the ability to use non-specific information, ease of working with the knowledge base, and obtaining the necessary knowledge.

One of the promising areas of application of expert systems in the energy sector is emergency control. In such cases, decisions are made based on fuzzy logic, possibility logic, and fuzzy sets.

Some attention is paid to accident prevention issues. Assessing the security of a regime based on the pace of the process remains a challenge. The difficulty lies in the fact that methods for assessing the state of the power system based on calculations of power flows are quite accurate, but require a long computer time. This led to a focus on approximate analytical methods, which led to the widespread use of expert systems. Such expert systems are based on well-deterministic mathematical models.

Restoring the normal functioning of power systems after accidents is an important task. The main difficulties are associated with their multivariance. In recent years, expert systems have been widely used to solve this problem. They help power system personnel restore operation after an accident. Since mode recovery is influenced by many factors, frameworks, inference systems, and object-oriented programming methods are used to represent knowledge. The proposed methods, based on the principles of artificial intelligence, provide satisfactory results for restoring modes after an accident.

Many expert systems have been developed to restore backbone networks after disasters. One of the main restoration criteria in such systems is to minimize power restoration time. Much attention is paid to the creation of expert systems that serve as advisers to the

power system dispatcher when restoring network operation after accidents. The power system dispatcher, processes warning and emergency signals, clarifies the operability of devices, and monitors the restoration of the network mode after eliminating the consequences of an accident. Expert systems significantly expand the capabilities of operational personnel in emergencies. In general, restoration of operation after a fault is quite a complex task, since many factors must be taken into account, such as frequency deviation, system voltage levels, power flow imbalance, etc.

Several works are devoted to the use of expert systems to ensure the reliable and safe operation of power systems. The problem of ensuring safety is one of the important ones in the operational control of power system modes. Many expert systems have been developed to solve this problem. For this purpose integrated systems are obtained by combining an automated dispatch control system and an expert system are also successfully used.

Expert systems are also often used to manage power system reliability. They are used to solve problems such as voltage regulation in power system nodes, control of power line overloads, and others.

Much attention is paid to the problems of filling the knowledge base when planning power system modes. The main method of acquiring knowledge is the method of drawing up protocols for specialist conversations when solving a problem. The advantage of this method compared to the interviewing method is that it takes into account the conditions of the problem being solved and the decision-making process. In the case of using the method of compiling conversation protocols, all actions of the specialist are recorded in the form of an action protocol. In this case, conversations between the specialist and the developer of the expert system are recorded. The knowledge base is obtained based on a joint analysis of the action protocol and the conversation protocol.

Distributed knowledge bases are often used in the control of energy systems. The use of distributed knowledge bases significantly improves the quality of dispatch control of power systems.

Three generations of expert systems designed to solve energy problems can be distinguished. The first generation of expert systems used rules, frames, or black box methods. The second generation of expert systems used a combination of these methods. In the third-generation expert systems, the following methods are used: the method of quick entry of conditions and conclusions, the method of prototypes, problem-oriented knowledge bases, the method of common simultaneous tasks, simple methods without detailing, and the method of hypertexts.

It should be noted that there are still no unified approaches to using expert systems in the energy sector, but their use is undeniable and highly effective when it is necessary to make decisions in the case of many options; when facts and data are incomplete or contain errors; When there is no closed model or such a model is difficult to use. Expert systems also allow the use of non-obvious information.

A review of existing literature shows that the main direction of research work is the control of operational and emergency modes, as well as the study of the use of expert systems in the process of restoring modes after accidents. Much less attention is paid to the creation and use of expert systems for multi-criteria control of daily normal modes of power systems.

Until recently, the problem of managing the daily regimes of power systems was solved as a single-criteria problem, in which the only criterion was the minimum total fuel costs. Naturally, this approach in many cases is not enough to correctly and completely reflect real processes. Since different situations give priority to different criteria, it is incorrect to always use the same criterion as the priority criterion. For example, the presence of the above criterion becomes meaningless in a deficit mode, since in such a situation the main task is to minimize the power imbalance of the power system, and not to minimize fuel costs, which will increase the already large power imbalance. In some cases, there is a need for water from the water control complex for non-energy purposes. This requires saving a certain amount of water, which makes the above criterion not important in this situation, etc.

In recent years, the problem of controlling normal daily regimes of power systems has been posed as a multi-criteria problem, which necessitates the use of the mathematical apparatus of vector optimization. In works [6-8], the problem of managing daily normal modes of the Georgian power system is solved as a multi-criteria control problem. The necessity of using the mathematical apparatus of multicriteria optimization and decision-making methods for multicriteria control of normal daily regimes of the power system is shown.

The complexity of the problem of multicriteria control of daily regimes of power systems is associated with large sizes; the variety of types of regulated power plants and the difficulty of taking into account the mutual influence of their modes; with the nonlinear nature of the dependencies used; with a large number of connection equations and the presence of restrictions such as equalities and inequalities; the probabilistic and uncertain nature of the initial information; requirements for the regime from the water management complex, taking into account which makes the task of managing everyday regimes difficult to formalize; the presence of contradictory and heterogeneous optimality criteria; difficulties in choosing an effective everyday mode from a variety of multi-criteria modes, etc.

In addition, the number of alternatives (modes) is large, which is due to the following factors: a) Load sequence of regulated hydroelectric power plants. Changing the load order gives the number of alternatives equal to $I!$. Here I is the number of regulated hydroelectric power stations; b) The loading sequence of regulated thermal power plants. Changing the loading sequence gives the number of alternatives equal to $J!$. Here J is the number of regulated thermal power plants; c) The order of loading one hydroelectric power station by hours per day. Changing the loading order gives the number of alternatives equal to $24!$. d) The order of loading one thermal power plant by hour per day.

Changing the loading order gives the number of alternatives equal to $24!$.

As we can see, the total number of alternatives is equal to $24!$. Added to this are many situations. From so many alternatives, we must choose one - the best.

Thus, in the area of effective control of energy systems, it is necessary to solve the following problems:

1. Formation of a clear system of goals and local criteria based on expert knowledge, and development of a mathematical model for managing energy systems.
2. Development of a set of effective control algorithmic tools, models, and decision-making schemes in multi-criteria systems.
3. Development of new types of network representations and information processing structures and construction on their basis of a specialized architecture (shell) of an expert system for multi-criteria control systems.

Conclusion

Thus, based on the above, we can make the following conclusions. The scope of application of expert systems in the energy sector is quite wide: planning of power system modes, control and control of electric power systems, restoration of power supply after an accident, identifying locations of faults in the power grid, analysis of power grid operating modes, control of flows in networks, forecasting, and planning of operating modes of equipment and systems dispatch control, dispatching of starts and stops of power units, design work, training of service personnel and advanced training, simulators, monitoring of power system states, generation of alarm signals, diagnostic systems, regulation of active and reactive power, control of the development of networks and systems, provision of reliable, safe modes power systems, etc.

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